

Information And Communication Technology (ICT) Compliance For Enhanced Management Of Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the current state of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) compliance for enhanced management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria and to identify the challenges facing the implementation of ICT compliance in these schools. Five research objectives, five research questions and five null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The theoretical frameworks of the study were based on Lewin-Schein's change theory, Shannon's communication theory and Schultz's human capital theory. The study adopted a descriptive survey study, the population covers all eight hundred and twenty (820) administrators (principals), a study sample of 272 administrators representing 34.2% arrived at using the Taro Yamane formula, stratified sampling techniques were used. The instrument's title, ICEMQ (ICT Compliance for Enhanced Management Questionnaire), 50 questionnaire items in modified Likert four points scale and ICEMAC (ICT Compliance for Enhanced Management Checklist), with an average reliability index of 0.71 were used to elicit information. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while z-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that awareness of ICT compliance, availability of ICT facilities, possession of relevant ICT skills, utilization of ICT facilities and challenges to ICT compliance significantly enhanced management effectiveness. The study concluded that ICT compliance is essential for the enhanced management of public senior The study concludes that ICT compliance is a critical factor in enhancing the management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria and recommended that educational administrators should ensure that ICT facilities are available and accessible to all staff members and that they are utilized effectively for administrative purposes. Schools should invest in ICT infrastructure, technical support and staff training to enhance ICT compliance.

Key word: Information and Communication Technology, compliance, management, secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

The current era is driven by knowledge and is continually evolving through innovative growth and advancements in technology. Ongoing improvements to the existing status quo are essential for both individuals and organizations to adapt to this trend and maintain relevance. Those who embrace Information and Communication Technology (ICT) will undoubtedly have a competitive advantage over their counterparts who do not. This is largely due to the pervasive influence of technology in today's world, necessitating a transition from outdated manual and analogue approaches to the requirements of

the contemporary digital landscape. Failure to make this shift can lead to frustration and obsolescence for individuals and institutions alike.

This underscores the importance of ICT compliance. In the context of managing public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and Nigeria as a whole, the effective utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become increasingly vital. ICT can significantly enhance school management, improve pedagogy, elevate teaching and learning, and promote student performance and achievement. This aligns with the findings of Uche (2020) and UNESCO (2018). However, compliance with ICT rules, regulations, and standards remains a significant challenge for these schools, as noted by the Nigerian Communications Commission (2019).

The availability of ICT facilities is another major challenge facing public senior secondary schools in Nigeria, as a whole (Rivers State Ministry of Education, 2019). Even when a lot has been committed into provision of ICT Facilities in schools, unfortunately many public Senior Secondary Schools in Nigeria lack ICT Facilities such as; Computers, Internet connectivity and Software, which indeed, impede on effective implementation of ICT in schools.

Possession of relevant ICT Skills is another essential factor in the effective implementation of ICT in public senior secondary schools unfortunately, many school administrations (Principals and Vice-Principals) in Nigeria, lack these relevant ICT Skills, leading to lack of expertise in the use of ICT (Kuada, 2015). The utilization of ICT Facilities in these public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, also another major challenge in the drive for ICT compliance (UNESCO, 2014). Many schools lack the necessary infrastructure and resources to support the effective use of ICT, which can lead to a lack of access to digital resource and opportunities.

Statement of the Problem

The effective management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, is hindered by a lack of compliance with information and communication technology (ICT) rules, regulations, and standards. While ICT has the potential to significantly enhance school management, many public senior secondary schools in the region are lacking qualified school administrators, such as principals and vice-principals. This failure to adhere to ICT compliance has serious implications for the quality of education offered to students and for various administrative functions. It can result in limited access to digital resources, insufficient preparation for students entering the digital economy, reduced competitiveness in the global marketplace, and inefficient administration.

In light of these issues, this study aims to investigate the current state of ICT compliance in Rivers State, Nigeria, and to identify the challenges impeding its implementation in public senior secondary schools.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigated the current state of ICT compliance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

In specific terms, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the level of awareness of ICT compliance among administrators (principals and vice-principals) in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria;
2. Assess the extent of availability of ICT facilities for administrative purposes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria;

Research Questions

1. What is the level of Awareness of ICT Compliance Among Administrators (Principals and Vice-Principals) in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?
2. What is the extent of Availability of ICT facilities in Schools for Administrative Purposes in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and vice-principals on the level of Awareness of ICT Compliance among Administrators (Principals and Vice-Principals) in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

2. There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and vice-principals as respondents on the extent of Availability of ICT facilities in Schools for Administrative Purposes in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study will provide a baseline data on the current state of ICT compliance in public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. It will also identify the challenges facing ICT compliance in public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. In addition, it will provide recommendations for improving ICT compliance in public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. It serves as source of information to policymakers and educators on effective ICT compliance strategies, enhanced school management practices through ICT adoption, improves teaching and learning outcomes and increases transparency and accountability in school administration. The findings and recommendations will be beneficial to educators, policy makers, researchers, students and communities, ultimately, supporting national development goals through education. The study also addresses a critical gap in education research, offering valuable insights for enhanced management and improved educational outcomes from Information and Communication Technology ICT compliance in public senior secondary schools.

Delimitation of the Study

The study is delimited to public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria; schools, principals and vice-principals (administrators) as participants and Information and Communication Technology, ICT compliance in administrative context. It is delimited to the following areas: awareness of school administrators (principals and vice-principals) of ICT compliance policies and procedures, ICT facilities available in these schools relevant. ICT skills possessed by school managers/administrators (principals and vice-principals); ICT facilities utilized by these administrators for administrative purpose and the challenges to ICT compliance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

Information and Communication Technology, commonly abbreviated as ICT, emerged from the concept of Information Technology (I.T.) in a 1958 article published in the Harvard Business Review by Harold J. Leavitt and Thomas L. Whistler. This viewpoint is supported by Abraham and Chukwu (2018), who assert that ICT is a system resulting from the intersection of Information Technology and Communication Technology (C.T.). This explains the various abbreviations and terms that have been applied to it, such as I.T.C. (Information Technology Communication) and C.I.T. (Communication Information Technology). Moreover, it is important to distinguish that ICT, as interpreted in this study, stands for Information and Communication Technology, which also encompasses aspects of Information Community Technology. Historically, long before the advent of ICT, humans have stored, retrieved, manipulated, and communicated information, tracing back to the development of the earliest writing systems. The formal introduction of the term Information and Communication Technology (ICT) was credited to Lord Dennis Stevenson in 1997, who expanded upon Information Technology to include educational contexts. This terminology took into consideration the emerging use of the internet and email in schools during that period. The acronym ICT was further popularized through a report by Lord Dennis Stevenson to the United Kingdom (U.K.) government in 1997, and played a significant role in the revision of the national curriculum in the year 2000 (Wikipedia, 2023).

In Nigeria, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) articulated its commitment to educational reform within the National Policy on Education (N.P.E.), specifically highlighted in the fourth edition of the document published in 2004. This edition was deemed essential due to significant policy innovations and the urgent need to update the preceding version from 1998. Among these pivotal innovations was the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into the educational framework, setting a progressive precedent for modern teaching methods.

Uche (2020) further elucidates the significance of the national policy for Information Technology (I.T.), which serves as a comprehensive strategy aimed at fostering the development of ICT in Nigeria. This

policy was meticulously crafted by the Federal Ministry of Service and Technology, officially released in March 2001. It encapsulates the Federal Government of Nigeria's vision regarding the role and potential of ICT, outlining how these technologies can be cultivated, applied, and the timeline designated for realizing Nigeria's ICT capabilities. In exploring the multifaceted nature of ICT, Ezechukwu, Osuala, and Gbobo (2022) define it as a rich array of technological tools and resources that facilitate communication, dissemination, storage, and management of information. Nwafor (2015) contributes to this discourse by presenting ICT as an interconnected network that continuously offers an expanding spectrum of services, significantly influencing the standardization of information within educational institutions. Yusuf (2015) broadens this understanding, describing ICT as encompassing not only computer hardware and software but also an array of networks and devices such as audio and video equipment, photography tools, and cameras, all of which transform information into accessible digital formats. Furthermore, UNESCO (2018) emphasizes that ICT represents the effective utilization of technology to manage, process, and disseminate information, underscoring its vital role in contemporary education and information systems.

Information and Communication Technology, I.C.T. Compliance

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) compliance, which will be referred to simply as ICT compliance in this study, consists of two distinct concepts: ICT itself and compliance. Compliance refers to adherence, conformity, and obedience to laws, rules, codes, regulations, and standards (Michalsons, 2023). For instance, software may be developed in accordance with specifications created by a standard-setting body and subsequently deployed by user organizations following the vendor's licensing agreement. In simple terms, compliance means following stipulated guidelines and established standards. ICT compliance encompasses the processes that ensure an organization's ICT systems adhere to relevant laws, regulations, contracts, and obligations (Racz, Weippl & Bonazzi, 2011). As noted by Rouse (2023), regulatory compliance requires that technology products, devices, services, and processes meet specific standards set by regulatory bodies. Failing to comply can result in hefty fines, litigation, and reputational damage. In Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy, through the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), is responsible for implementing all forms of ICT compliance (Thomas, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic exposed the ICT readiness and preparedness of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, highlighting their level of ICT compliance before, during, and after the pandemic. During this time, many schools were completely shut down, leaving vulnerable students, who were preparing for external examinations like the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) administered by the West African Examination Council (WAEC), the Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) by the National Examination Council (NECO), and the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) by the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB), without alternatives. The pandemic exacerbated the existing challenge noted by Allison & Ojedapo (2011), who observed that there was insufficient time to cover the syllabus and prepare students for these external examinations, likely resulting in mass failures in many subjects. ICT compliance, defined as adherence to regulatory requirements, standards, and best practices in the use and management of ICT systems (Khan et al., 2020), ensures that these systems are secure, reliable, and efficient while supporting the organization's goals and objectives. It is crucial for maintaining the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of information (Sadia et al., 2019). According to Alenezi et al. (2020), ICT compliance mitigates risks associated with ICT systems, such as cyber-attacks, data breaches, and system failures.

In educational institutions, ICT compliance is particularly essential, especially in public senior secondary schools (Adeyemo et al., 2019). It ensures the security and integrity of students' data, protection against cyber threats, and support for online learning. In Nigeria, NITDA is responsible for regulating ICT compliance (NITDA, 2020) and has developed guidelines and standards for compliance across various sectors, including education. Furthermore, Rivers State has made significant efforts to promote ICT compliance in public senior secondary schools (Rivers State Government, 2020).

Awareness of ICT Compliance Policies and Procedures

Knowledge serves as a vital foundation for overcoming life's challenges, acting as a transformative power that can rescue individuals from various predicaments. This principle is powerfully articulated in the

Bible, particularly in Hosea 4:6, which poignantly states, "My people are destroyed for lack of knowledge: because thou hast rejected knowledge, I will also reject thee that thou shalt be no priest to me" (KJV). Awareness, as defined by the Cambridge Online Dictionary (2023), is a noun signifying both the recognition that something exists and the comprehensive understanding of a particular situation or subject grounded in current information or personal experiences. Governments often take the initiative to create awareness as a means of keeping the populace adequately informed about critical issues affecting their lives. This approach is encapsulated in the popular adage, "if you are not informed (aware), you are deformed which underscores the importance of being knowledgeable and engaged.

In the specific context of enhancing the management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, it is imperative to prioritize the establishment of awareness regarding the myriad advantages that Information and Communication Technology (ICT) can bring. This step must be taken before any computer facilities are introduced into educational institutions. The Federal Republic of Nigeria's National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) further supports this initiative, stipulating in Section 12, Subsection 118(d) that the government is committed to promoting the dissemination of information on innovative and progressive educational principles and practices. This dissemination can take various forms, including publications, workshops, meetings, seminars, and conferences. Establishing awareness is not a mere formality; it is a crucial strategic element that involves engaging all relevant stakeholders, including educational authorities, teachers, parents, students, and policy-makers. Each of these groups plays a vital role in the successful implementation of ICT as an integral tool for enhancing management in public senior secondary schools. Given that ICT represents a relatively new frontier in education, fostering a thorough understanding among these stakeholders is essential for driving effective integration and ensuring that ICT becomes a catalyst for educational improvement in Rivers State, Nigeria. Such concerted efforts will pave the way for innovative educational management practices, ultimately benefiting the entire school community.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study covers all the eight hundred and twenty (820) administrators (principals), that is, 268 principals and 552 vice-principals in the entire two hundred and seventy-six (276) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The sample size used for this study was 280 respondents, representing 34.2% of the total population. This was arrived at using Taro Yamane formula. The stratified sampling technique was considered suitable because of the large size of the population. The instrument used in this study was self-developed for the collection of data. Two researcher-designed instruments, titled, *ICT Compliance for Enhanced Management Questionnaire (ICEMQ)* was used for the study. The instrument for this study was given face and content validation by the researcher's supervisors in the Department of Educational Management and another expert from the Department of Educational Measurement and Evaluation, Psychology, Guidance and Counseling, in all in the Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. To ensure that the research instruments measured consistently what it was designed to measure, the instruments were trial tested using 20 respondents made up of 10 principals and 10 vice-principals, who were not part of the study. The data generated were used for reliability estimates and the coefficient established at an average of 0.71. This high reliability index indicated that the instruments were reliable. The researcher administered two hundred and eighty (280) copies of the instruments. This was done with the help of two research assistants. The research questions were answered using **mean** and **standard deviation** which are simple descriptive statistics while the null hypotheses were tested at various degrees of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance using **z-test**.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the level of awareness of ICT compliance among administrators (principals and vice-principals) in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria and how is it related to enhanced management?*

Table 1 Mean scores on the level of ICT compliance awareness among School Administrators

S/N	Variables	Principals (72)		Vice- Principals (200)		Decision	
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂		\bar{x} Set
1.	I am aware of ICT compliance policies and procedures in my school	2.72	1.13	2.61	1.21	2.67	Agree
2.	ICT compliance training has improved my management skill	2.96	1.17	2.79	1.23	2.88	Agree
3.	Awareness of ICT compliance has reduced ICT related risks in the school	2.81	1.15	2.73	1.15	2.77	Agree
4.	ICT compliance awareness has influenced my decision making as a school administrator	2.82	1.15	2.88	1.01	2.85	Agree
5.	ICT compliance awareness has improved communication among stakeholders in my school	2.90	1.10	2.85	1.13	2.88	Agree
6.	I believe ICT compliance is essential for school management	2.69	1.19	2.97	1.06	2.83	Agree
7.	awareness of ICT compliance has enhanced data security in my school	2.61	0.97	2.89	1.17	2.75	Agree
8.	ICT compliance awareness has improved overall school performance	2.54	1.26	2.86	1.05	2.70	Agree
	Grade \bar{x} and SD	2.76	1.14	2.82	1.13	2.79	

Source: *Field survey, 2024*, \bar{x} =Mean; SD=Standard deviation, ≥ 2.50 accept, otherwise reject

Result in Table 1 above shows the mean response of respondents (Principals & Vice- Principals) on the level of ICT compliance awareness among administrators principals and vice-principals) in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria and how is it related to enhanced management. Respondents have mean score between 2.54 and 2.90, which is above the criterion mean of ≥ 2.50 . This indicates that respondents agreed to be aware of ICT compliance; with the benefit and risks. The average mean score for principals and vice- principals were 2.76 and 2.82, respectively. This indicates that respondents with regards to items 1-8, agreed with awareness of ICT compliances' alongside its benefit and risk for public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: *To what extent are ICT facilities available for administrative purposes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Mean scores on availability of ICT Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools

S/N	Variables	Principals (72)		Vice- Principals (200)			Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD ₁	\bar{x}_2	SD ₂	\bar{x} Set	
9.	Our school has sufficient computer for administrative task	2.71	1.16	2.55	1.15	2.63	Agree
10.	The internet connectivity in our school is reliable	2.94	1.03	2.88	1.08	2.91	Agree
11.	ICT facilities have improved teaching and learning in our school	2.51	1.14	2.72	1.22	2.62	Agree
12.	Our school's ICT infrastructure supports effective data management	2.72	1.06	2.68	1.03	2.70	Agree
13.	ICT facilities have enhanced communication among stakeholders in our school	2.74	1.13	2.63	1.15	2.69	Agree
14.	Our school has adequate software for administrative task	2.76	1.13	2.57	1.29	2.67	Agree
15.	ICT facilities have improved students' engagement and participation	2.71	1.04	2.67	1.12	2.69	Agree
16.	Our school's ICT facilities are well maintained	2.67	1.01	2.56	1.06	2.62	Agree
17.	ICT facilities have reduced administrative task processing time	2.65	1.26	2.80	1.05	2.73	Agree
18.	Our school's ICT infrastructures supports online learning platform	2.97	1.09	2.58	1.19	2.78	Agree
19.	ICT facilities have improved teachers' productivity	2.85	1.12	2.69	1.20	2.77	Agree
20.	Our school's ICT facilities are accessible to all stakeholders	3.19	1.04	2.58	1.11	2.89	Agree
Grade \bar{x} and SD		2.79	1.10	2.66	1.14	2.73	

Source: Field survey, 2024, =Mean; SD=Standard deviation, ≥ 2.50 accept, otherwise reject

Result in Table 2 above shows the mean response of respondents (Principals & Vice- Principals) on the extent ICT facilities available for administrative purposes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Respondents have mean score between 2.51 and 3.19, which is above the criterion mean of ≥ 2.50 . This indicates that respondents agreed that significant computer system, reliable internet connectivity, among others for administrative purposes enhances management of schools. The average mean score for principals and vice- principals were 2.79 and 2.66, respectively. This indicates that

respondents with regards to items 9-20, agreed that there were ICT facilities available for administrative purposes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis

HO₁ There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and vice- principals on the level of awareness on ICT compliance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4.6: z-Test Analysis on the level of awareness of ICT compliance in Public Senior Secondary Schools

Categories	n	\bar{x}	SD	α	df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Principals	72	2.76	1.14	0.05	270	0.38	1.96	Accept
Vice Principals	200	2.82	1.13					

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 4.6 shows that principals had mean and standard deviation score of 2.76 and 1.14, while vice-principals had 2.82 and 1.13 respectively. The z-cal value was 0.38, while the z-crit was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance for two tailed test. This result shows that z-cal was less than z-crit, therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This shows that, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and vice- principals on the level of ICT compliance awareness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and vice- principals on the extent ICT facilities are available for administrative purposes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Table 4.7: z-Test Analysis on availability of ICT Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools

Categories	n	\bar{x}	SD	α	df	z-cal	z-crit.	Decision
Principals	72	2.79	1.10	0.05	270	0.85	1.96	Accept
Vice Principals	200	2.66	1.14					

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 4.4 shows that principals had mean and standard deviation score of 2.79 and 1.10, while vice-principals had 2.66 and 1.14 respectively. The z-cal value was 0.85, while the z-crit was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance for two tailed test. This result shows that z-cal was less than z-crit, therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. This implies that, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and vice- principals on the extent ICT facilities are available for administrative purposes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Awareness of ICT Compliance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

The findings of this study reveals that both principals and vice-principals agree in all items 1-9 as the level of awareness of ICT compliance among administrators (principals and vice principals) in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. These include awareness of ICT policies and procedures; awareness that ICT training improves management and awareness of ICT compliance reduces ICT-related risks, which all enhance management of these schools. Others are awareness of ICT compliance improves communication among stakeholders, influences decision making, is essential for effective school management, enhances data security and improves overall school performance, which all predicts enhanced management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Also, there is

no significant difference between the mean ratings scores of principals and vice- principals on the level of ICT compliance awareness in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. Supporting is Ojokheta (2009), who carried out study in identification of the competencies needed by teachers for the development and implementation of ICT based education. Data were collected through the use of questionnaire and analyzed using frequencies and percentages. Sonic personal, pedagogical and subject oriented/tactical competencies were identified. Among there commendations was that the Federal Government should make the development of Information and Communication Technology competencies of teachers a priority and set targets when teachers should become Information and Communication Technology illiterates to mandatory standards.

Availability of ICT Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria.

The finding of this study in 9 – 17 reveal that their various mean values were above the criterion mean of 2.50 by the principals and vice-principals on the extent of availability of ICT facilities for administrative purposes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. These include sufficient computers for administrative tasks, reliable internet connectivity, ICT facilities for improved teaching and learning in schools, adequate ICT software for administrative tasks, ICT facilities for effective data management, enhanced communication among stakeholders; improved student engagement and participation and the need for routine check and maintenance of these ICT facilities. Also, there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of principals and vice- principals on the extent ICT facilities are available for administrative purposes in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. In line is Osinem and Nwojie (2010) who investigated the extent of availability of ICT resources for quality assurance of Business Education in South-West Nigeria The study is aimed at assessing the extent of availability of ICT resources for quality assurance of Business Education in South-West Nigeria. The findings of this study revealed that ICT resources are available at a low extent for quality assurance of business education in universities in South-West Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that ICT compliance is a critical factor in enhancing the management of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings suggest that schools that prioritize ICT compliance tend to have better management practices and outcomes. Therefore, policy makers and educational administrators should prioritize ICT compliance as a strategic tool for improving management practices in public senior secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Policymakers and educational administrators should prioritize ICT awareness band compliance as a strategic tool for improving management practices in public senior secondary schools. Schools should develop and implement ICT policies that promote compliance and effective utilization of ICT facilities.
2. The government should provide adequate funding and support for ICT infrastructure and technical support in public senior secondary schools.

Contribution to Knowledge

The findings of this study contributes to the body of knowledge on ICT compliance for enhanced management of public senior secondary schools. Furthermore, policymakers, educational administrators and researchers will find this study very insightful.

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